

Phishing Website Detection Using Machine Learning Algorithms

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Abstract—Phishing is the most commonly used social engineering and cyber-attack. Through this attack fraud that target carrying confidential information including usernames, passwords, financial information (credit cards or bank accounts), with the purpose of using it fraudulently. People are still being trapped into revealing sensitive information in phishing website. Phishing is becoming more hostile day by day and its detection is incredibly important. One of the reliable methods for identifying the phishing website is using machine learning algorithms. This study examines a number of various models, and chooses the model that will most accurately identify phishing website.

Keywords—phishing, machine learning Techniques, Random Forest

I. INTRODUCTION

A phishing website is a popular social engineering approach that imitates reliable URLs and online sites. Phishing is a form of fraudulent activity that includes creating a false website that impersonates a genuine one in order to steal sensitive or private data from users. Attackers frequently utilize phony websites to lure victims into clicking on them so they may steal their login information, password, credit card details, and other private and personal information. These attacks on phishing are profitable for these attackers as well. Their typical targets include e-commerce apps, e-payment systems, and e-banking platforms. Because phishing assaults rely on victims' weaknesses, they are difficult to protect against. It's imperative to advance phishing detection methods.

The common technique, commonly referred to as the "blacklist" method, for detecting phishing websites involves adding Internet Protocol (IP) blacklisted URLs to the antivirus database. Attackers utilize clever methods to deceive people by changing the URL to seem authentic through obfuscation and many other straightforward tactics, such as fast-flux, in which proxies are automatically constructed to host the website, algorithmic production of new URLs, etc. This method's primary flaw is that it cannot identify phishing attacks that are launched at zero hour.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Phishing is the unlawful act of pretending to be a reliable source in an electronic message in order to obtain private data, such as usernames, passwords, and credit card numbers. [1]. To improve the model's accuracy, the suggested model utilizes an adaptive boosting strategy that

makes use of several classifiers [4]. To enhance the accuracy of phishing website identification, the feature selection technique is paired with an ensemble learning strategy based on several regression and classification models [2]. Machine Learning for Phishing Website Detection Considered for identifying phishing sites is the detection of phishing websites using machine learning features [3]. Literature on the detection of phishing attacks [5].

III.METHODOLOGY

1.DATA SET DESCRIPTION

The URLs dataset used to extract features. The variables that were derived are categorized into:

- a. Address Bar based Features
- b. Domain based Features
- c.HTML & JavaScript based Features

a.Address Bar Based Features

- Domain of the URL

There are various features to be extracted and considered address bar foundation features. The following were chosen from among them for this project.

- Using IP

URLs with IP addresses suggest someone is attempting to steal sensitive data. The value assigned to this feature is 1

(phishing) if the domain portion of the URL contains an IP address, or 0 otherwise (legitimate).

- The "@" sign in a URL

It checks if the URL includes the "@" symbol. Using the "@" sign in a URL causes the browser to disregard anything before the "@," and the actual address frequently comes after the "@." If the URL contains the symbol "@," the value assigned to this feature is 1 (phishing), otherwise it is 0. (legitimate).

- Short URL

Phishers can mask lengthy phishing URLs by reducing them with the help of short URL services. The aim is to direct consumers to phishing websites.

- Prefix, suffix (-)

Evaluating if the URL's domain has the symbol "-." Legitimate URLs never use the dash symbol. Prefixes or suffixes, separated by, are routinely added to the domain name by phishers (-) to give consumers the impression that they are visiting a trustworthy website.

- Redirection "/" in URL

It verifies whether the URL contains the character "/" If there is any "/" in the URL route, the user will be sent to another website.

- Favicon

It is a very appealing website about websites. Is displayed in the address bar, the webpage is unquestionably a phishing attempt.

b. Domain based Features

Data extraction is yet another domain-based function.

- DNS Record

This feature's rate is set to 1 (phishing) if the DNS record for a phishing website is blank or cannot be identified; otherwise, it is set to 0. (legitimate).

- Web Traffic

By observing the number of visitors and the number of pages they view, this feature analyzes the popularity of the website.

- Age of Domain

Most phishing attempts only keep operating for a brief period of time. Any domain considered to be acceptable for this project must be at least 12 months old. The difference between the introduction and expiry times is simply referred to as age in this context.

- End Period of Domain

The remaining website time is calculated by subtracting the current time as from expired date.

c. HTML and JavaScript based Features

The dataset also helps make use of JavaScript and HTML-based features.

- IFrame Redirection

Another website can be inserted inside the one that is now being shown using the HTML element IFrame. The "iframe" element enables phisher to conceal or remove frame borders from fraudulent activities. Phishers instruct the browser to create a visual distinction in this situation by using the "frameborder" function.

- Status Bar Custom

Scammers can use JavaScript to manipulate users into seeing a false URL in status bar. Before we can extract this functionality, we need to check the website source code,

specifically the "on Mouseover" event, to identify if it modifies the status bar.

- Disabling Right Click

Phishers utilize JavaScript to separate right-click capabilities, preventing users from seeing and storing the website source code. The same guidelines that apply to "Using on Mouseover to hide the link" also apply to this functionality. We will still search the webpage source code for the event "event.button==2" to see if the right click is disable.

- Website Forwarding

The thin line that separates trusted websites from phishing ones is how frequently a website has been redirected. In our dataset, we find that reliable websites have never seen more than one reroutes.

2.DATA PREPROCESSING

Data process involves operations including cleansing, instance selection, feature extraction, normalizing, transformation, and more. The training dataset is the end product of data preparation. Pre-processing of the data may affect how the final processing's findings are understood. Data cleaning might involve filling in the gaps in the data, reducing noise, identifying and eliminating outliers, and addressing incompatibilities. A technique called data integration may include adding particular databases or data sets. Data transformation is the process of gathering and normalizing data in order to measure a certain set of data. Data preparation includes cleaning, instance selection, and feature selection. By conducting data reduction, we may obtain a view of the dataset that is extremely tiny in size but, which helps to create the same output of the study.

3.TRAIN-TEST SPLIT

In order for the training dataset to be utilized to detect phishing websites on the testing dataset, the dataset is divided into two subsets: testing set and training set. To help the training model efficiently train and understand the data, 30% of the data for the testing set is examined.

4.MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

A seven-machine learning classification model are using here:

a. Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a prediction study. It is frequently used to visualize data and emphasize the connection between a dependent binary and one or more independent nominal, ordinal, interval, or ratio-level variables. Is used to predict the likelihood of a binary answer based on one or more independent factors. It implies that logistic regression is used to predict a result that has two values, such as 0 or 1.

b. K-Nearest Neighbour

The K-Nearest Neighbor method is the most basic supervised learning-based machine learning technique. The algorithm searches the training set for the nearest data points to forecast a new data point. The closest neighbor's positive number is K. The distance between two nearest neighbours is known as the Euclidean distance.

The Euclidean distance between two points A and B can be calculated using the formula:

$$d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) = d(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \sqrt{(q_1 - p_1)^2 + (q_2 - p_2)^2 + \dots + (q_n - p_n)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_i - p_i)^2}$$

c. Decision Tree Classifier

One of the most popular machine literacy algorithms is the decision tree. It is a classification model based on supervised learning. It's simple to understand and put into action. With an internal node that represents the dataset's characteristics, branches that represent the decision-making process, and a leaf node that indicates the result, it has a tree-like structure. The features of the supplied dataset are used to inform the choice or test.

d. Support Vector Machine

SVM is a useful tool for researching the set of rules that are used to both regression and type difficulties. Each statistics set is shown in n-dimensional space when using SVM. By identifying the hyperplane that distinguishes particular classes, we perform type.

e. Random Forest

It is a tool for learning a set of regulations applied to class and regression data. The forest is created using the random forest algorithm using a variety of decision trees. High detection accuracy is provided by a large number of trees. This approach may be used to any dataset. It works by building a variety of decision trees while training and producing the regression of discrete trees or the mode of the classes.

f. XGBoost

XG Boost is the abbreviation of Extreme Gradient Boosting. Gradient-boosted decision trees for quick and effective. Models are added one after the other until we determine that no more improvement is possible. The purpose of this approach is provided efficient memory and computational resources. The goal of this design was to make the most effective use of the sources that could be used to train the model.

g. AdaBoost

Adaptive boosting is represented as AdaBoost. It is a meta-machine learning approach. AdaBoost model's key benefit is that it is quick, easy, and quick to execute. Any machine learning algorithm may be combined with the method due to its flexibility. To get at the classification it has the ability to turn weak predictors or learners into powerful classifiers.

IV.IMPLEMENATATION AND RESULT

The work is implemented using the Jupiter environment, and dataset is collected from UCI machine learning repository. And also, two separate datasets are created, such a dataset for training and testing. The classifier models are executed using the Sklearn module. Python allows the models to be evaluated and trained using the collected data and the precision of the relevant calculated algorithms is

used. The classifier models are implemented using the sklearn package. Python enables the evaluation and training of the models utilizing the gathered data and the accuracy of the pertinent. The algorithms are calculated.

To ensure the highest level of accuracy, A number of classifier and ensemble approaches are applied to evaluate and train the phishing website detection model. After all algorithm have returned their results, each algorithm will provide their estimated accuracy. Each algorithm is compared against others to see which offers the greatest accuracy rate, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison Table

Classifiers	Accuracy	Precision
Logistic Regression	0.9281	0.90
K-NN	0.9273	0.93
Decision tree	0.9491	0.94
Random Forest	0.9654	0.95
SVM	0.9441	0.95
AdaBoost	0.9142	0.90
XGBoost	0.9486	0.92

Figure 6. Comparison of all ML algorithms.

V.CONCLUSION

The objective of this research is to use machine learning classification models to enhance the detection of phishing website. We use the random forest approach to get a detection accuracy 96.5%, while the lowest accuracy used in XGboost is 91.4. The results also show that classifier performance has improved as more data is used as training data. Online phishing provides a greater risk. The strategy created is a useful tool for identifying phished websites and might inspire the creation of more robust anti-phishing measures in the future.

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